

INTEGRATED SKILLS IN COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Annotation: This article reveals main peculiarities of Communicative Language Teaching methodology. An author tries to investigate what is integrated-skills, its importance and role in teaching process. Moreover, the article contains different views and opinions of linguists about integrated-skills and Communicative Language teaching process and methodology. The idea of the integrated-skill teaching approach is not new and has long been discussed and supported by various researchers.

Keywords: Integrated skills, methodology, ILL, ELF, Communicative Language teaching, speaking, writing, reading, listening.

Integrated Skills focuses on the four main English skills - reading, writing, speaking and listening - through a “Communicative Language Teaching” methodology. New grammar patterns are learned in the context of a conversation or a real-life situation. Students will engage in various activities to practice English including listening tasks, role playing, and stimulating discussions. The integrated-skills approach, which incorporates listening, speaking, reading, and writing, has become a new trend in EFL contexts because it is believed an effective approach to develop students' communicative competence and the ability to use English to gain access to social, vocational, educational, or professional opportunities. Different from the traditional segregated language skills approach which presented a language skill in isolation from the others, the integrated-skills approach presents all language skills in conjunction with each other so that the learners do not only know the language they are learning but also are able to use it natural communication. This article reviews current studies and ideas related to integrated skills approach in order to provide a more vivid understanding of its implementation in EFL contexts. The idea of the integrated-skill teaching approach is not new and has long been discussed and supported by various researchers (Shanahan & Lomax, 1988;Fitzgerald & Shanahan, 2000;Al-Dosari, 2016). The Integrated-skills teaching pedagogy is a natural learning approach because it helps in accelerating the development of communicative skills in EFL students (Li & Yang, 2014;Mekheimer & Aldosari, 2013;Pysarchyk &

Yamshynska, 2015;Pardede, 2017). Li & Yang (2014) write, "Reading and writing are both the communicative means between the reader and the writer".

According to Pardede (2017), "To enable the EFL students to develop their knowledge of English and their competence to use it in real communication, implementing the integrative skills approach is unavoidable" (p. 218).

Previous studies asserted that ILL needs the learners' good understanding of the sources being learned, as using the language for communication must be automatically interwoven somewhat like a tapestry (Oxford, 2001;Orellana, 2001;Pardede, 2017). Oxford (ibid) proposes that to integrate the language skills instruction, teachers should consider the following stages: (1) Learning more about the various ways to integrate language skills in the classroom (e.g., content-based, task-based, or a combination); (2) Reflecting on their current approach and evaluate the extent to which the skills are integrated; (3) Choosing instructional materials, textbooks and technologies that promote the integration of listening, reading, speaking and writing as well as the associated skills of syntax, vocabulary and so on; (4) Integrating the other language skills through appropriate tasks; (5) Teaching language learning strategies and emphasizing that a given strategy can often enhance performance in multiple skills. Basically, integrated skills are to integrate one language skill with another language skill. Carols (1990) in Pardede (2017) outlines five advantages of integrated skills; first, skills integration provides continuity in teaching/program learning because in this approach tasks are closely related to each other; second, activities in the integrated skills approach can be designed to provide input before output; third, it provides realistic learning as skills integration allows for the development of four skills within a realistic communicative framework; fourth it provides chances to know and redeploy the language learned by students in different contexts and modes and it can be valuable because it allows for the recycling and revision of languages which has already been taught; fifth, skills integration increases confidence to a weaker or less confident learner.

Used literature:

1. Oxford, 2001; Orellana, 2001; Pardede "Teaching Methodology and its peculiarities "
2. Shanahan & Lomax, 1988; Fitzgerald & Shanahan, 2000; Al-Dosari, 2016 "Main problems of Integrated Methodology "
3. Li & Yang, 2014; Mekheimer & Aldosari, 2013; Pysarchyk & Yamshynska, 2015; Pardede, 2017

